

ISic3578

Honours for Heia Melpo, priestess of Augusta

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble (pink)

Object

tabula

Editor

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Autopsy

2011.06.15

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Excavated in 1971, from room 7 of the west portico in the agora

Coordinates

37.997856, 14.262463

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory 30598

Physical Description

A slab of pink breccia-like marble, with dark grey veins. Intact at the top, left and right, but the lower part is missing; the surviving upper part is broken in two pieces which have been joined together. Front and rear faces are smooth. The edges are rough, and have been lightly cut back on the reverse, presumably for fixing in a wall or monument; there are traces of mortar on the reverse. Holes (for fixing pegs?) are preserved in the right edge (10.5 cm from the top) and the top edge (one 7cm from right corner, a second 12.5 cm from left corner).

Dimensions

Height 28.6 cm

Width 49-49.5 cm

Depth 3 cm

Layout

The front preserves two lines of Latin text, with a large vacat above, but the second line is only partially preserved. It is impossible to know how much has been lost from the lower half.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are relatively tall and narrow, deeply cut and somewhat irregular, with plain triangular serifs and triangular interpuncts. E has lightly upward pointing bars, of equal length; A is taller than the other letters (70 mm); all the hastae are off-vertical in M; P is open. Guide lines are visible.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 60-65 mm

Line 2: 55 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. Heiae · Melponi ·
2. Sacerdoti · augušta,ε

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation (en)

(Set up for) Heia Melpo, priestess of Augusta ...

Commentary

Although the stone is missing at the very start of line 2, there is no reason to think that anything is lost before the initial S. Despite the loss of the lower part of the line, the reading is clear except at the very end of the line. The lack of space towards the line-end has led the engraver to link the top of the S and the T, effectively in ligature. The final two letters are less certain: there are three separate marks preserved; the first is clearly a triangular apex, and surely an A; the second mark looks to be incidental damage rather than part of a letter stroke (the compression of letters would be extreme if it were part of a letter); the final mark looks to be a very short horizontal, with an upward serif at the end, which is most compatible with the top of an E, albeit a very short one, to be explained by the desire of the engraver to fit the word in before the edge of the stone. Priestesses of the Augusta are more commonly described as sacerdos divae Augustae, but instances of sacerdos Augustae are also attested (e.g. ILS 6486 [www.trismegistos.org/text/514268] , Aeclanum; AE 1998 no. 416 [www.trismegistos.org/text/261126] , Interamnia Praetuttiorum; AE 1971 no.79 [www.trismegistos.org/text/250392] , Formiae). For a survey of Italian examples of priestesses of the imperial cult, see Granino Cecero, M.G. 2007. Flaminicae e sacerdotess del culto imperiale nell'Italia romana: primi esiti di una ricerca in corso. In *Acta XII Congressus Internationalis Epigraphiae Graecae et Latinae*, II, 643-54. Priestesses in Sicily are attested at Termini (ISic0100 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0100>]) and Gozo (ISic3469 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3469>]) and Messina (ISic0267 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0267>]). Cult for Livia post-dates AD 42 (but this text need not reference Livia specifically), and this text presumably therefore dates to the later first or second century AD.

The Greek name Melpo(n) is not common in either Greek or Latin epigraphy (here in the Latinised dative), with the form Melpon (Μέλπωv [http://classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/lgpn_search.cgi?namenoaccents=%CE%9C%CE%95%CE%9B%CE%A0%CE%A9%CE%9D]) only attested for men (including once at Lipara, ISic2847 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic2847>]); the female form Μελπώ [<http://www.lgpn.ox.ac.uk/id/V4-31221>] is only known from Phagres in Macedonia.

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Bibliography

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